

A CULTURE OF PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND TEACHING IT.

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Abstract. *This article will discuss vocational training has become a topical issue today. To solve this problem, it is necessary to carefully develop a methodology for teaching terminology. A natural question arises: what should be done (s) to overcome the difficulties encountered in teaching the terminological vocabulary of a foreign language. The development of systematic analysis emerged in the middle of the twentieth century with the emergence of scientific and technical tasks.*

Keywords: *knowledge, spiritual education, systematic approach, systematic analysis, vocational training, professional terms.*

КУЛЬТУРА ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО ОБЩЕНИЯ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ И ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ ЕГО.

Аннотация. *В данной статье пойдет речь о профессиональном обучении, которое стало актуальным на сегодняшний день. Для решения этой проблемы необходимо тщательно разработать методику обучения терминологии. Возникает закономерный вопрос: что нужно сделать(а) для преодоления трудностей, возникающих при обучении терминологической лексике иностранного языка. Развитие систематического анализа возникло в середине XX века с появлением научно-технических задач.*

Ключевые слова: *знания, духовное образование, системный подход, системный анализ, профессиональная подготовка, профессиональные термины.*

In all speeches of President Sh.M.Mirziyevov a systematic approach to the problem, critical analysis, raising the work in all areas to a qualitatively new level, increasing the efficiency of the existing system, raising the system of public administration to the level of modern requirements based on today's and tomorrow's requirements. attention is paid to issues such as improving the entire system of performance. In this regard, it is desirable that each person responsible for the training of personnel in accordance with modern requirements, a systematic approach to the problem, a systematic organization of pedagogical and scientific activities.

In these days of rapid development of science and rapid growth and frequent updating of scientific and technical information, improvement of engineering structures and technological processes, increasing the level of automation in management systems, the transition to a system of training at the undergraduate academic level problems occur. In fact, these problems are due to the fact that the amount of workload allocated to the student is significantly reduced compared to previous years.

The second aspect of the problem is that compliance with the requirements of the State Education Standards must be unconditionally ensured.

The only way to solve such scientific and pedagogical problems is the introduction of person-centered educational technologies in the educational process, which is one of the most pressing tasks in educational practice.

At the same time, in the era of rapidly accelerating globalization in the international labor market - high technology, mass information, digitalization in real sectors of the economy, the flow of information is rapidly entering social life in our country and is widespread. One of the most pressing issues facing the education system is the rapid receipt of information, its analysis, processing, synthesis, summarization and, ultimately, the achievement of guaranteed results in education by referring to the judgment of students.

Naturally, such a comprehensive, goal-oriented process requires the technologicalization of the educational process.

Although the use of person-centered innovative technologies reduces the workload, while maintaining the integrity of the content and quality of education, the educational process will be significantly accelerated in accordance with the requirements of the time, and efforts will be aimed at achieving guaranteed results.

The essence of the technology of person-centered education is that it takes into account the interests of all participants in the educational process - the full development. This, of course, when planning the educational process in advance, of course, is the competence of one individual participant in the process - not to improve the knowledge and practical skills of the individual, but to develop the knowledge and practical skills of all participants. It is also necessary to take into account the need to take the symptoms to a higher level.

Therefore, in the organization and implementation of educational processes in the discipline of "Resistance of Materials" it is expedient to use the types of person-centered education: modular, computerized, interactive, problem-based, innovative.

Empirical methodology for the development of professional competencies, methods of their assessment, issues of creating a learning environment for their formation, in particular, the research conducted by G. Cheetham, M. Daniels, J. Jarmul developed methods of forming a culture of professional speech, substantiated theoretical approaches to professional training; a model of professional competence formation was created; psychological aspects of management activities were analyzed.

Igna O.N. In his research work, he demonstrated the development of students' sociocultural competencies in career-oriented education on the basis of authentic materials in the German language material. Polyakov O.G. Developed the concept of career-oriented English education. Different aspects of the formation of professional communication skills in students of non-philological higher education institutions in the process of teaching foreign languages (English, German, French, Russian) Russian scientists A.Petrov, L.Mark, M.Dementeva, Kasyanenko LS,

Systematic analysis is a relatively young and, at the same time, rapidly evolving science.

The reason for its rapid development is determined by the scale of the demand for education, the growing need for science to solve complex problems, the development of systemic projects. The development of systematic analysis emerged in the middle of the twentieth century with the emergence of scientific and technical tasks. The main role in this is played by the processes of analysis, knowledge and practical application of complex objects.

Systematic analysis was used as an independent research area in the 1950s and 1960s in the United States to perform major business tasks such as technical development of the armed forces, space exploration, improvement of public administration, distribution of production capacity, labor and equipment demand, and product needs. However, in the 1960s and 1970s, the introduction of systems analysis methods into calculators provided an opportunity to create theoretical models as tools for performing complex tasks. As the conditions for intensive use of system analysis capabilities have expanded, target-planning program management methods have been created. In particular, in order to solve this or that problem, special programs are developed that take into account human and material resources in the organization of the organization's activities. As a result, different schools of systemic analysis have emerged that focus on researching the activities of different fields.

Vocational training has become a topical issue today. To solve this problem, it is necessary to carefully develop a methodology for teaching terminology. A natural question arises: what should be done (s) to overcome the difficulties encountered in teaching the terminological vocabulary of a foreign language? In order to accelerate the formation (intensification) and increase efficiency (optimization) of the formation of speech skills of students of non-philological higher education, the most necessary (remember: according to the principle of necessity and sufficiency) terms are taught (without them it is impossible to explain complex language units); terminology is given in the form of a scientific system. J. Jalolov schematically demonstrated the terminology studied in the framework of scientific and methodological criteria: **(Figure 1)**.

Classes on specialty subjects observation of the process, from the professional knowledge of students in this process during the study of the content of activities aimed at informing witnessed a situation where, although management and other sciences in the process of training organized by teachers ensuring the overall development of students, their enrichment of spiritual and moral qualities and worldview, as well as deciding on situations such as the formation of professional

qualifications in them. Although special attention is paid to the work of finding, the role of spiritual education, importance, the need to study spirituality by students and

etc. a theoretical or practical approach to the continuous, purposeful coverage of issues necessary. The direction of management education is extremely important in teaching students a culture of professional communication in their language so that they can use industry terms correctly in speech. Based on this, we have developed a three-step system for developing skills in using industry terms. This system is aimed at the gradual introduction of terms from the passive vocabulary of students to the active vocabulary. To do this, we developed exercises and tasks that can be used at each stage, from simple to complex, and divided them into the following types (Figure2):

Figure 2. A three-step system of teaching students to work with industry terms. Conclusion.

Now in Uzbekistan, along with the native language, knowledge of English and Russian is a great help in the field of specialization and expands the study of achievements in the field. Due to the fact that most of the professional information comes in Russian and English, today the priority for the specialist is to know these languages, with information in English, to get the necessary information from text and communication. The main factor today is to help management students to fully understand the meanings of terms and new words in the field, as well as to develop a culture of communication, such as in the process of learning and practical activities. The proposed system consists of the initial, intermediate, and advanced stages, and the exercises and assignments applied should form a whole. It is known that there are dialogic and monologue forms of speech, and the mentioned components of professional communication competence are manifested in one or both forms of speech. It is recommended to follow this step-by-step sequence in the growth and development of professional monologue and dialogic speech in research work.

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